

OXIDE/OXIDE COMPOSITE FIBERS FOR ENHANCED CREEP RESISTANCE

Vincent H. Hammond, Frank E. Wawner, and Dana M. Elzey

*Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Virginia,
Thornton Hall, Charlottesville, Virginia, 22903, USA*

SUMMARY: Aluminum oxide multi-filament tows may be produced at relatively low cost, but are limited by poor creep strength at elevated temperatures. This study compares the creep behavior of alumina tow-fibers with that of recently developed oxide/oxide CMC fibers. The CMC fibers tested were fabricated by infiltration of an alumina tow with an alumina powder slurry, followed by outgassing and sintering. The resulting alumina matrix is highly porous (roughly 50% of theoretical density), but is found to exert a strong influence on the fiber's mechanical properties. While uniaxial creep tests conducted at 1100 °C revealed similar creep stress exponents (of around three) for both plain and CMC fibers, the composite fibers exhibited dramatically improved failure strains and time-to-failure. The origins of this enhanced creep behavior are discussed in terms of the composite fiber architecture and sintering treatment.

KEYWORDS: tow-fiber, alumina, oxide/oxide composite, creep

INTRODUCTION

Although oxide/oxide composites are considered ideal candidates for elevated temperature use due to their excellent oxidation resistance, their use has been limited by the high cost of available reinforcements. The problem associated with cost has been largely overcome through the development of alumina tow-fibers (or fiber bundles) produced by a low-cost sol-gel technique. This approach results in an approximate 50-fold reduction in cost relative to large diameter alumina monofilaments (i.e., Saphikon).

However, polycrystalline alumina fibers possess the lowest creep resistance of any ceramic fiber currently considered for high temperature use [1]. The poor creep response has been attributed to rapid grain boundary diffusion (Coble creep) resulting from the fine grain size. Evidence also suggests that grain-boundary sliding contributes significantly to the total strain observed during creep deformation of polycrystalline alumina [2].

The development of a tow-based oxide/oxide ceramic matrix composite (CMC) fiber offers a possible approach for improving the creep response of tow-fibers. In this study, a partially sintered (porous) alumina matrix is incorporated into an alumina tow-fiber, resulting in the creation of a CMC fiber. The presence of the porous matrix in the CMC fiber is expected to promote mechanisms such as fiber bridging, crack deflection, and possibly load transfer to

improve the high temperature mechanical response of the bundle. It also prevents unwanted infiltration of reactive metallic matrices when processing metal matrix composites.

A similar approach has been used by researchers at 3M, who impregnated a Nextel 610 tow with graphite followed by heat treatment [3]. The resulting CMC fiber was then incorporated into a Ti-6Al-4V matrix [3]. Although measured tensile strengths of this metallic matrix composite system were in reasonable agreement with values predicted using a rule of mixtures approximation, the creep behavior was not investigated.

This paper will discuss work currently underway to characterize and compare the creep response of an Al_2O_3 tow-fiber and an $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ CMC fiber. Experimental results are presented which indicate significant improvements in creep properties offered by CMC fibers, depending on heat treatment and matrix fraction. The influence of processing conditions on creep properties and possible mechanisms for the improved creep resistance are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nextel 610 is the specific tow-fiber (approximately 400 filaments/tow) selected for this investigation. Nextel 610 filaments are >99.5 wt% alumina, with an average diameter of 12 μm , a tensile strength of 3.0-3.5 GPa, and a grain size less than 0.1 μm . Individual filaments are spun from a viscous aluminum salt slurry using a multi-orifice spinnerette. After the organic volatiles are removed, the filaments are converted to the desired α -phase by heat treating at 1400 °C, then collected into a multi-filament tow-fiber [4].

Initial experiments performed on as-received Nextel 610 tow-fibers generated baseline data for comparison with the creep response of CMC fibers. The bundle cross-sectional area was determined by dividing the bundle weight/length (g/cm) by the density of alumina (3.9 g/cm³). The stress on the tow-fiber was then determined by dividing the applied load by this area.

The CMC fiber characterized in this study was prepared by drawing the Nextel 610 tow through a slurry containing a suspension of micron-sized alumina powder particles. The fiber was then shaped and the organic binder burned off, resulting in a green fiber, which was then subjected to a heat treatment of approximately 1 minute at a sintering temperature (T_s) of 1100 °C or 1400 °C. The first set of CMC fibers tested were prepared using a 15 vol% Al_2O_3 slurry. Recent CMC fibers have been produced using a higher content (49 vol%) alumina slurry.

A representative SEM micrograph for each fiber is shown in Fig. 1. The volume fraction of the matrix, V_M , for the CMC fiber produced using the 15 vol% slurry was calculated to be 33%. In the case of the newer CMC fiber, the calculated matrix volume fraction is 66%. Two important features regarding the CMC fibers are: 1) there is approximately 40% fine porosity in the matrix and 2) the number of Nextel 610 filaments is the same for both CMC fibers (approximately 400).

Fig. 1: SEM micrographs of a) 33% V_M CMC fiber and b) 66% V_M CMC fiber.

The creep test apparatus consisted of an induction heater with a nickel susceptor to heat the fiber sample. (A similar approach utilizing a graphite susceptor has been used to test commercial grade and low oxygen content Nicalon fibers in argon [5,6].) Each end of the fiber was attached to tabs located outside the hot zone using high strength epoxy. A constant load was applied after the fiber was heated to the desired test temperature. Sample elongation was measured by an LVDT, which produces a voltage proportional to the elongation of the filament as a function of time. All creep tests were conducted in air at 1100 °C.

RESULTS

Representative creep curves for tow-fibers tested at 1100 °C are shown in Fig. 2. These curves indicate that the tow enters secondary, or steady-state, creep almost immediately upon loading, with a region of tertiary creep signaling imminent failure. Although failure times varied significantly, from 15 minutes ($\sigma = 385.5$ MPa) to 28 hours ($\sigma = 124.5$ MPa), the response of the tow-fiber was similar in each case.

Fig. 2: Representative creep curves for Nextel 610 tow-fibers.

Determining the cross-sectional area of the CMC fiber for calculating the applied stress is complicated by incomplete infiltration of matrix into the tow, the presence of matrix porosity, and the unlikelihood of significant load-carrying capability by the matrix. Therefore, the area of the CMC fiber was assumed to be equal to that of the uninfiltreated bundle. Arguments in support of this assumption, which is equivalent to assuming the matrix carries no load, are presented below.

A comparison between the as-received Nextel 610 tow and the 1100 °C-sintered CMC fiber tested at various loads at 1100 °C is shown in Fig. 3. The most noticeable difference between the two sets of curves is the increase in failure strains of the CMC fibers relative to the Nextel 610 tow-fiber. This difference is a factor of 2 at the highest stress, dropping to a factor of 1.2 at the lowest stress. By comparing the slope of the steady-state creep regime, it can be seen that the creep rates for as-received tows and CMC fibers are nearly identical. Indeed, the similarity in creep rates for the two fiber-types supports our previous suggestion regarding the load carrying capacity of the matrix.

Fig. 3: Comparison of creep response for Nextel 610 and 33% V_M CMC fiber.

A comparison of creep curves generated from tests at 1100 °C/385.5 MPa for the as-received Nextel 610 tow and 33% V_M CMC fibers sintered at 1100 and 1400 °C is shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen that sintering at 1400 °C dramatically lowers the steady-state creep rate. To a lesser degree, sintering at 1400 °C also increases the failure strain relative to the uninfilted tow. These two improvements result in greater than a factor of 25 increase in time-to-failure for the 1400 °C-sintered CMC fiber relative to the as-received Nextel 610 tow. This substantial reduction in creep rate and corresponding increase in creep life occurred over the entire range of applied stresses used during testing (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 4: Influence of $T_s = 1400$ °C on creep response of 33% V_M CMC fiber.

To determine if the improvement in the creep response of the 1400 °C-sintered CMC fiber resulted only from changes in the matrix, a series of tests were performed on uninfilted Nextel 610 tows sintered at 1400 °C. A comparison of results obtained from the specific test condition of 1100 °C/385.5 MPa for each of the four fibers is given in Table 1. Multiple tests were performed at these conditions on the Nextel 610 tows, both in the as-received and

sintered condition, with single tests on the CMC fibers. Thus, the reproducibility of the results for the CMC fibers is not well defined. However, the data presented for the 33% V_M CMC fibers followed the observed trends in measured creep rate for the 5 tests performed (see Fig. 5).

Table 1: Comparison of creep response of Nextel 610 tows and CMC fibers.
(T_s = sintering temperature, $T = 1100$ °C, $\sigma = 385.5$ MPa)

Fiber	ϵ_f	t_f (seconds)	$\dot{\epsilon}_{ss} \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Nextel 610 tow, as received	0.0532	1022	39.29
Nextel 610 tow, $T_s = 1400$ °C	0.0116	545	10.25
33% V_M CMC fiber, $T_s = 1100$ °C	0.1109	2435	40.59
33% V_M CMC fiber, $T_s = 1400$ °C	0.0730	26613	1.939

From the data, it can be seen that there is a significant reduction in the steady-state creep rate for the tow sintered at 1400 °C. However, there is still a 5-fold reduction in creep rate between the 1400 °C-sintered Nextel 610 tow and the 1400 °C-sintered CMC fiber. Moreover, there is a greater than 50% reduction in failure strain for the Nextel 610 tow sintered at 1400 °C compared to the as-received tow. This is in contrast to the approximately 33% increase in failure strain for the 1400 °C-sintered CMC fiber compared to the as-received tow.

Fig. 5: Comparison of steady-state creep rates for all fiber types subjected to various sintering treatments.

The stress exponent for each fiber type can be found by determining the slope of a linear regression curve fit to each set of data. These values are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of the stress exponents for each fiber tested at 1100 °C.

Fiber	n
Nextel 610 single filament [7]	3.0
Nextel 610 tow, as received	2.9
Nextel 610 tow, $T_s = 1400$ °C	4.7
33% V_M CMC, $T_s = 1100$ °C	3.2
33% V_M CMC, $T_s = 1400$ °C	2.3
66% V_M CMC, $T_s = 1100$ °C	3.1

The stress exponents are similar for the Nextel 610 single filament, the tow-fiber, and the two

CMC fibers sintered at 1100 °C. There is an approximate 20% reduction for the CMC fiber sintered at 1400 °C, while a dramatic increase (> 50%) is observed for the heat-treated tow relative to the as-received tow-fiber.

The creep response of Nextel 610 single filaments has been characterized by Wilson *et al* [7]. They found that the steady-state creep rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_{ss}$, of single filaments could be expressed by the power-law creep relation

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ss} = A\sigma^n \exp\left[\frac{-Q_a}{RT}\right] \quad (1)$$

where A is a pre-exponential constant, σ is the applied stress (ksi), n is the stress exponent, Q_a is the activation energy, R is the universal gas constant, and T is the temperature (Kelvin). Wilson *et al* [7] determined the constants and material parameters in Eqn (1) to be $A = 2.944 \times 10^{15}$, $n = 3$, and $Q_a = 660$ kJ/mole. Using Eqn (1) with these values and a test temperature of 1100 °C, the steady-state creep rate for Nextel 610 single filaments was compared with the tow and 33% V_M CMC-fiber creep rates measured from experiment. Fig. 6 indicates that Eqn (1) provides a good approximation for the response of the Nextel 610 tow-fiber and the 1100 °C-sintered CMC fiber. However, the equation drastically over-predicts the creep rate of the CMC fiber sintered at 1400 °C.

Fig. 6: Steady state creep rates as a function of applied stress at 1100 °C for Nextel 610 and 33% V_M CMC fibers.

A comparison of results between an as-received Nextel 610 tow and the 33% V_M and 66% V_M CMC fibers sintered at 1100 °C is shown in Fig. 7. The steady-state creep rate for the recently prepared 66% V_M CMC fiber is noticeably lower compared to the other two fibers (see Fig. 5). In addition, the strain to failure of the 66% V_M CMC fiber has dropped to a value only slightly improved over the as-received tow (0.0649 vs. 0.0532, respectively). The time to failure of the two CMC fibers is approximately the same (40 minutes), with the degree of tertiary creep not as pronounced in the 66% V_M CMC fiber compared to the 33% V_M CMC fiber or the Nextel 610 tow-fiber.

Fig. 7: Influence of increased matrix content on the response of the $T_s = 1100$ °C CMC fibers.

DISCUSSION

The creep tests on Nextel 610 tows were motivated by the fact that relatively little research has been done to characterize the creep behavior of ceramic tow-fibers and to provide a basis for understanding the more complicated CMC fiber response. The tertiary creep observed in the tow-fiber tests represents a structural response of multifilament tows, and is not observed in tests on single filaments of Nextel 610 [7]. Tertiary failure has been recorded in tests of other tow-fibers, including FP and PRD-166 bundles [8]. The presence of tertiary creep in fiber bundles is attributed to an increase in the effective applied stress due to progressive failure of individual filaments within the tow.

Creep rupture of Nextel 610 single filaments has been found to occur through the nucleation of cavities on grain boundaries which then coalesced to form macroscopic cracks [7]. Cavities were located throughout the gauge length in filaments which did not exhibit necking prior to failure, or concentrated primarily at the rupture location for filaments which experienced necking.

An early study on the creep of fine-grained alumina indicated that both Nabarro-Herring and Coble creep occurred during deformation, with Coble creep being the primary mechanism of deformation [9]. This observation was supported by a later study [10] which noted that Nabarro-Herring creep did not contribute significantly to the creep of fine-grained (1.6 μm) polycrystalline alumina. In both cases, experimental strain rates were lower than those predicted by Coble creep mechanisms. This led to the conclusion that creep was governed by an interface-controlled diffusion mechanism, in which the creation/destruction of vacancies at the grain boundaries became rate controlling. Grain boundary cavitation and occasional triple point offsets were observed [11], suggesting that the grain boundary region became more important as the grain size was reduced. This conclusion was supported by a later study [2], which determined that the contribution of grain-boundary sliding to the creep strain of polycrystalline alumina was approximately 70%. Therefore, the high value determined for the stress exponent of Nextel 610 single filaments ($n = 3$) was attributed to the combined effects of the fine grain size of the filament (leading to interface-controlled diffusional creep), the presence of cavitation, and grain sliding [7].

The excellent agreement between the measured creep rates for the tow-fiber and the calculated rate for single filaments (Eqn 1) indicates that the as-received tow-fiber creeps as a collection of single filaments, with a negligible degree of filament interaction (Fig. 6). On the other hand, as-received tows sintered at 1400 °C displayed both a significant reduction in the steady-state creep rate and a reduction in strain-to-failure (Fig. 5, Table 1). This may be explained as follows: as shown by recent research, Nextel 610 tow-fibers subjected to elevated temperature heat treatments develop multi-filament clusters, consisting of several filaments sintered together [12]. Provided the inter-filament bond is strong enough, a crack could propagate from one filament to the adjoining filaments within that cluster, resulting in the simultaneous failure of multiple filaments. Indeed, it has been observed during room temperature tensile testing that these clusters often fail on or near the same fracture plane [12]. In addition, the creation of weld lines on the surface of the filaments introduces numerous surface defects. These new defects act as additional strength limiting flaws leading to a reduced failure strength of the filament, and consequently lower the time-to-failure for the heat treated tow-fiber.

The tendency to form multi-filament clusters may also provide some insight into the reduction of the steady-state creep rate seen in the 1400 °C-sintered tow-fibers. A small degree ($\pm 3^\circ$) of filament misalignment typically exists in the as-received tow-fibers [13]. This misalignment results in some filaments remaining unloaded initially. Through sintering of individual filaments, an initial loading condition where all filaments are equally loaded is more likely. This uniform loading would serve to reduce the creep rate observed during testing. Another factor which will influence the creep rate is the grain size of the individual filaments. Grain size analysis showed an increase from 69 nm for the as-received filaments to 91 nm for filaments sintered at 1400 °C [12]. Assuming Coble creep is the primary mechanism controlling creep response, the growth in grain size would result in an approximate 3-fold reduction in creep rate as compared to the 4-fold reduction observed. Thus, changes in filament microstructure and bundle structure can explain the dramatic change in stress exponent measured for the heat-treated tow relative to the as-received tow (Table 2).

When compared with Nextel 610 tow-fibers tested under similar conditions, the 33% V_M CMC fibers sintered at 1100 °C possessed nearly identical steady-state creep rates (Figs. 3, 5). Therefore, creep rates calculated using the single filament creep equation (Eqn (1)) are also in excellent agreement with experimentally measured creep rates for this CMC fiber (Fig. 6). It is important to note that the stress used in calculating the predicted creep rate was obtained by dividing the applied load by the area of the filaments. The observed agreement between the creep rates of as-received tows and CMC fibers supports the earlier assumption that the porous matrix does not carry significant load in 1100 °C-sintered CMC fibers.

One explanation for the low load-carrying capacity of the matrix is the extensive microcracking observed in interrupted creep tests. SEM observation of the CMC fiber surface at locations far removed from the failure location revealed the presence of severe matrix microcracking normal to the applied load (i.e., normal to the filaments). Creep tests on 66% V_M CMC fibers sintered at 1100 °C were interrupted when a certain percentage of the expected failure strain was reached. Matrix microcracks were found to have initiated as early as 15% of the failure strain. Both the density and severity of microcracking increased as the fiber was tested to progressively higher strains. These observations indicate that the failure strain of the matrix is substantially lower than that of the filaments and that the matrix does not carry significant load. Continued matrix cracking probably occurs as a result of load transfer from the filaments to the matrix.

The 33% V_M CMC fiber sintered at 1400 °C displayed a significant reduction in steady-state creep rate compared to the as-received tow and 1100 °C-sintered CMC fiber. However, test results from 1400 °C-sintered tows indicate that approximately 75% of the reduction in creep rate for this CMC fiber results from changes in filament microstructure and tow architecture caused by sintering. In addition, sintering the as-received tow at 1400 °C introduces numerous defects and bonded filaments, resulting in a severe reduction in the strain-to-failure. In spite of this, the CMC fiber does show some improvement in strain-to-failure relative to the as-received tow. This combination of a modest improvement in strain-to-failure and the 20-fold reduction in creep rate leads to a greatly extended creep life.

Although the creep rates for the 66% V_M CMC fibers are lower than 33% V_M CMC fibers for a sintering temperature of 1100 °C, the stress exponents for each fiber are nearly identical to that of the single filament (Table 2). This agreement in stress exponents suggests that the creep rate is still controlled by the single filament response and that no significant load transfer is occurring between the filaments and matrix. Therefore, an alternative mechanism must be responsible for the improvement in strain-to-failure and the corresponding increase in the creep life of the CMC fibers compared to the as-received Nextel 610 tow.

The improved failure strain and absence of tertiary creep in CMC fibers may be explained as follows. In Nextel 610 tows, an unequal load distribution results from the misalignment that exists initially between filaments. This leads to premature failure of some filaments, resulting in progressively higher loads on surviving filaments and the tertiary creep observed in bundle tests. However, the matrix in the CMC fiber promotes a more evenly distributed loading condition by constraining transverse motion of the filaments (filament rearrangement). This ensures that each filament experiences a nearly identical stress and corresponding strain rate. The uniform loading, by suppressing premature failure of individual filaments (except for low strength filaments), also accounts for the reduction in the severity of the tertiary creep regime in CMC fibers.

CONCLUSIONS

The creep response of oxide/oxide CMC fibers produced through infiltration of an alumina tow-fiber with a porous alumina matrix has been studied as a function of matrix volume fraction and sintering temperature. Creep of the as-received tow-fiber and CMC fibers sintered at 1100 °C was found to be controlled by the creep response of single filaments. Although the porous matrix appears not to contribute significantly to the load carrying capability of these CMC fibers, the matrix promotes a uniform loading condition among individual filaments. This results in increased creep failure strain and a reduction in the severity of the tertiary creep regime relative to the as-received tow-fiber. Because of a significant reduction in steady-state creep rate and a marginal improvement in strain-to-failure, CMC fibers sintered at 1400 °C showed a dramatic increase in creep life relative to as-received tows and CMC fibers sintered at 1100 °C. The exact interaction between the filaments and the porous matrix during the deformation of CMC fibers is the subject of ongoing research.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank H. Déve and D. M. Wilson of 3M and P. E. Cantonwine of the Materials Science Department at the University of Virginia for their helpful comments and discussions.

REFERENCES

1. R. E. Tressler and J. A. DiCarlo, "High Temperature Mechanical Properties of Advanced Ceramic Fibers," *High Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites (HT-CMC-1)*, ed. by R. Naslain, J. Lamon, and D. Doumeingts, 1993, pp. 33-49.
2. A. H. Chokshi, "An Evaluation of the Grain-Boundary Sliding Contribution to Creep Deformation in Polycrystalline Alumina," *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 25, 1990, pp. 3221-3228.
3. P. E. Cantonwine and H. Déve, "Longitudinal Stress/Strain Response of Al₂O₃/Ti6Al4V Continuous Fiber Composites," *Recent Advances in Titanium Metal Matrix Composites*, ed. by F. H. Froes and J. Storer, 1995, pp. 201-212.
4. M. M. Vogel-Martin and D. M. Wilson, "Properties of Seeded Sol-Gel Alumina Fibers," *Proceedings from the 16th Conference on Metal Matrix, Carbon, and Ceramic Matrix Composites*, NASA Conference Publication #3175, part 2, 1992, pp. 519-533.
5. R. Bodet and J. Lamon, "Creep Testing of Ceramic Fibers at High Temperature in a Controlled Environment or Air," *Proceedings of European Conference on Composites Testing and Standardization, ECCM-CTS 2*, Hamburg, Germany, 1994, pp. 385-396.
6. R. Bodet, X. Bourrat, J. Lamon, and R. Naslain, "Tensile Creep Behavior of a Silicon Carbide Based Fiber with a low Oxygen Content," *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 30, 1995, pp. 661-677.
7. D. M. Wilson, D. C. Lueneburg, and S. L. Leider, "High Temperature Properties of Nextel 610 and Alumina-based Nanocomposite Fibers," *Ceramic Engineering and Science Proceedings*, Vol. 14, No. 7-8, 1993, pp. 609-621.
8. D. J. Pysher and R. E. Tressler, "Creep Rupture Studies of Two Alumina-based Ceramic Fibers," *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 27, 1992, pp. 423-428.
9. R. M. Cannon, W. H. Rhodes, and A. H. Heuer, "Plastic Deformation of Fine-Grained Alumina: I, Interface Controlled Diffusional Creep," *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 63, 1980, pp. 46-53.
10. A. H. Chokshi and J. R. Porter, "High Temperature Mechanical Properties of Single Phase Alumina," *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 21, 1986, pp. 703-710.
11. A. H. Heuer, R. M. Cannon, and N. J. Tighe, in *Ultrafine-Grain Ceramics*, ed. by J. J. Burke, N. L. Reed, and V. Weiss, 1970, pp. 339-65.
12. P. E. Cantonwine and H. N. G. Wadley, "The Mechanical Response of Sintered Alumina Bundles and Porous Alumina Matrix Composites," (*to appear in*) *Symposium on Ceramic Matrix Composites*, American Ceramic Society Meeting, Cincinnati, OH, May 3-6, 1998.
13. H. Déve, 3M Company, private communication, 1998.